

Optimize Neural Network Implementation on FPGA

(Mengoptimumkan Pelaksanaan Rangkaian Neural Pada FPGA)

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ABSTRACT

The use of Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) is growing rapidly in various field. Due to its reconfigurable ability, FPGA have become one of the essential components in data processing and communication systems such as implementing artificial neural network into FPGA. Recent developments in computing technology not only influenced software filed but also helped the use of custom logic design in hardware platform, namely Hardware/Software (HW/SW) Co-design System. In general, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) are highly-efficient and accurate for classifying the objects. One type of CNN is called Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN). In this study, RCNN is the network selected to implement the HW/SW system. The Viola-Jones algorithm is also very useful for object detection and this algorithm can be achieved and implemented in Matlab software. In addition, the HW/SW system runs in Zynq-7000 SoC hardware with AXI DMA and ARM processor. The hardware system design has been achieved for data transfer from PL to PS and save the data to BRAM memory. In addition, CNN IP core which represents the CNN architecture as well as weight and bias of network layers, especially convolutional layer and fully connected layer also been planned. Face recognition application for embedded software system will also be designed for face classification and prediction. In this study, RCNN has been successfully designed and trained. Subsequently, it is implemented in hardware for use in the embedded software application. Hardware implementation was achieved with a maximum FPGA usage of 67 18k BRAM, 115 DSP48E, 10779 FF and 17102 LUT with an on-chip power consumption of 1.879 Watts. This meets the resource requirements of the FPGA. The results show that the artificial neural network can be implemented in FPGA to achieve hardware implementation of face recognition system.

Keywords: FPFA; CNN; Face recognition; HW/SW co-design

ABSTRAK

Penggunaan Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) berkembang pesat dalam pelbagai bidang. Oleh sebab kemampuan untuk dikonfigurasi semula, FPGA telah menjadi salah satu komponen yang penting dalam sistem pemprosesan data dan komunikasi seperti melaksanakan rangkaian neural pada FPGA. Perkembangan teknologi pengkomputeran baru-baru ini tidak hanya mempengaruhi perisian tetapi juga membantu penggunaan reka bentuk logik tersesuai pada platform perkakasan, iaitu reka bentuk sistem perkakasan dan perisian (HW/SW). Secara umum, rangkaian neural konvolusi (CNN) adalah sangat cekap dan tepat untuk mengklasifikasikan objek. Salah satu jenis CNN ialah Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN). RCNN dipilih untuk melaksanakan sistem HW/SW dalam kajian ini. Algoritma Viola Jones juga sangat berguna untuk mengesan objek dan boleh dilaksanakan dalam perisian Matlab. Sistem HW/SW dijalankan dalam perkakasan Zynq-7000 SoC dengan AXI DMA dan ARM pemproses. Reka bentuk sistem perkakasan telah dirancang untuk pemindahan data dari PL ke PS dan simpan data ke memori BRAM. Selain itu, blok IP CNN yang mewakili seni bina CNN dan juga data berat dan bias juga telah dirancang. Algoritma pengecaman wajah untuk sistem perisian terbenam dalam FPGA juga akan dirancang untuk klasifikasi dan ramalan wajah. Dalam kajian ini, RCNN telah berjaya direka bentuk dan dilatih dan seterusnya melaksanakannya dalam perkakasan untuk digunakan dalam aplikasi perisian terbenam. Pelaksanaan perkakasan telah dicapai dengan penggunaan maksimum FPGA sebanyak 67 18k BRAM, 115 DSP48E, 10779 FF dan 17102 LUT dengan penggunaan kuasa cip 1.879 Watts. Ini memenuhi keperluan sumber FPGA. Hasilnya menunjukkan rangkaian neural dapat dilaksanakan dan dicapai dalam FPGA untuk melaksanakan sistem pengecaman wajah

Kata Kunci: Pemandu; FPGA; CNN; Pengecaman wajah; Reka bentuk Bersama HW/SW

INTRODUCTION

A security recognition system that will use physical features such as a person's face, fingerprints and iris have been considered primarily for the security system called 'Biometric system'. In facial recognition algorithm, artificial neural network is used in this study because it is useful and popular for classifying complex data such as face data. Neural network classifiers can be used in a variety of applications such as facial recognition. It requires huge works to develop an algorithm that able to process and classify the images efficiently.

ANN are very useful because they have strengths and numerical values which can perform more than one task or job at the same time. However, due to lack of tools to port CNN on the FPGA, the purpose of this thesis is to outline the overall resources and tools available to implement CNN facial recognition into the FPGA.

Viola-Jones algorithm which detects the predefined features that can be found in the images. This algorithm consists of Haar features, integral images, Adaboost training and classifier cascading to achieve face detection. Defining the key features and using them in optimal way is the hardest part in this algorithm (Smriti Tikoo & Nitin Malik 2016). In contrast to defining features, CNN algorithm is used to learn the features from the huge image dataset. To detect and recognize the objects precisely, CNN had to perform an intensive computing operation with floating point numbers.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) are an information processing paradigm, which is inspired by the way biological nervous systems, such as brain, to process the information. CNN had become increasingly popular for being able to run the tracking and object recognition on specific tasks and easy to build compared to other algorithms.

Modern computer science creates connection-based systems that used to model the biological neurons as nodes and perform various interactions between network components. It is performed by the use of weight, bias and activation function. Neural network can perform tasks without being programmed precisely and performance can be improved by data learning. The neural network consists of nodes (such as brain neurons) and are interconnected in the input layer, hidden layer and output layer. Nodes are determined by weight and bias while function activation is specified to activate the output.

The implementation of CNN model on FPGA is due to they offer a flexible and energy efficient solution. FPGA based computing architecture can be reconfigured with parallel capabilities are very useful for implementing neural networks. In this study, the design for data transfer from Programmable Logics (PL) and Processing Systems (PS) to DDR memory had been discussed. The entire Hardware/Software Co-design of FPGA with block IP CNN and processor ARM will be implemented in the platform Vivado.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is divided into two levels. The first stage is Matlab-based facial recognition system using the Viola-Jones algorithm and RCNN. The second stage is Hardware/Software (HW/SW) implementation.

Figure 1 : Flow of Matlab-based face recognition

First, collect faces from 2 different individuals as dataset. Each database consists of 400 cropped face images of 300×300 pixels. The total dataset will be divided by 2, which are 640 training dataset and 160 testing datasets. Second, detect the face in the image by using the Cascade Object Detector which is based on Viola-Jones algorithm in the Matlab. Next, design and train the RCNN. Figure 2 shows the architecture of RCNN which is built of 15 network layers in total which are input layer, convolutional layer, ReLU layer, Max Pooling layer, Fully Connected layer, softmax layer and output layer.

No	Layer type	Activation function
1	Input image	96×96×3
2	Convolutional	23×23×6
3	ReLU	23×23×6
4	Max Pooling	11×11×6
5	Convolutional	11×11×16
6	ReLU	11×11×16

7	Max Pooling	4×4×16
8	Convolutional	4×4×16
9	ReLU	4×4×16
10	Max Pooling	2×2×16
11	Fully Connected	1×1×100
12	ReLU	1×1×100
13	Fully Connected	1×1×2
14	Softmax	1×1×2
15	Classification output	-

Table 1 : Architecture of RCNN

After the design of RCNN, train the network to classify the faces from the dataset by following the training parameter which is showed as Table 2. The training parameter includes training type, minimum batch size, initial training rate and maximum epoch.

Training type	sgdm
Minimum batch size	128
Initial training rate	0.00001
Maximum epoch	5

Table 2 : Training Parameter

After the training of RCNN, start extracting the weight and bias from each network layers, especially Convolutional layers and Fully Connected layers in the form of matrices which is showed as Table 3. A parameter file which includes the weight and bias in the form of matrices is created for the use of C-based hardware design of the CNN module.

No	Layer type	Weight	Bias
1	Input Image	-	-
2	Convolutional	5×5×3×6	1×1×6
3	ReLU	-	-
4	Max Pooling	-	-
5	Convolutional	5×5×6×16	1×1×16
6	ReLU	-	-
7	Max Pooling	-	-
8	Konvolusi	5×5×16×16	1×1×16
9	ReLU	-	-
10	Max Pooling	-	-
11	Fully Connected	100×64	100×1
12	ReLU	-	-
13	Fully Connected	2×100	2×1
14	Softmax	-	-
15	Classification Output	-	-

Table 3 : Weight and Bias of RCNN

For Hardware/Software co-design, Zedboard Development Kit is chosen as the hardware platform which is showed as Figure 2. This board includes Xilinx Z-7020 chip and its specification are showed as Table 4. It consists of Programmable Logics (PL), Look Up Tables (LUT), Flip Flop (FF), Block Random Access Memory (BRAM) and Digital Signal Processing (DSP) slices. For the CNN IP core design, the available RAM usage is 4.9 Mb.

Figure 2 : Zedboard Development Kit

Device Name	Z-7020
Body Part	XC7Z020
Xilinx 7 Series Programmable Logic (PL)	Artix-7 FPGA
PL cells	85K
LUT	53200
FF	106400
BRAM	4.9 Mb
DSP Slices	220

Table 4 : Zynq-7000 SoC Specification

For the C-based hardware design of CNN IP core, the platform used is Vivado HLS. The module designed can be used to classify the class of objects from the input image by using deep learning algorithm. A neural network code is written and created for the use of synthesis of CNN IP core in C programming language and HLS script. In this study, AXI4 stream interface is chosen for communication system in the CNN IP core. The AXI4 stream includes TDATA, TSTRB, TKEEP, TLAST, TID, TDEST and TUSER. Table 5 shows the bandwidth of signal required for the design of CNN IP core.

AXI4 Stream Signal	Bandwidth
TDATA	32
TSTRB	4
TKEEP	4
TLAST	0
TID	0
TDEST	0
TUSER	0

Table 5 : AXI4 Stream Signal Bandwidth

Once the CNN IP core is successfully generated, it is imported to the Vivado Design Suite for hardware block diagram design. Figure 3 shows the top-level functional diagram of hardware system.

Figure 3 : Hardware System Diagram

From Figure 3, DMA is used to transfer the data from memory to CNN IP core and then back to the memory. Processor ARM and DDR memory controller behaves within Zynq PS while CNN IP core and AXI behaves within Zynq PL. AXI-lite bus allows processor interacts with AXI DMA to control, start and monitor the data transfer. AXI_MM2S and AXI_S2MM are memory-mapped AXI4 bus which provide accessibility of DMA to DDR memory. AXIS_MM2S and AXIS_S2MM are AXI4 stream bus which allow dataflow without memory address.

After the hardware block diagram is successfully validated, start generation of bitstream and export the bitstream to the Vivado SDK. For the HW/SW implementation, an embedded HW/SW system design is required for face recognition by using CNN and it is written in C programming language.

Figure 4 : HW/SW Embedded System for DMA Read Transaction

Figure 5 : HW/SW Embedded System for DMA Write Transaction

DMA transaction is a completed I/O operation such as single read and write request from the application. Allocated buffer within the DMA can be divided within the memory without continuous allocation from the DDR memory controller. For the DMA, MM2S is used for data transfer from DDR memory to FPGA while the S2MM is used to transfer the data to DDR memory. In this study, DMA read and write transaction for the HW/SW embedded system are showed as Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 6 shows the flow chart for C-based face recognition application used in this study. Before the embedded software implemented into the FPGA, the system already includes the hardware system design with CNN IP core. First, choose an input image in the form of hexadecimal into the C application. After that, read the image bytes and label. If the system fails to read them, it will back to the start. Otherwise the system starts the face recognition with label to predict the class of the given image.

Figure 6 : Flow Chart of Face Recognition Application

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the results are obtained after 2 stages. First stage is Matlab-based face recognition and the second stage is HW/SW implementation.

Figure 7 : Graph of RCNN Training

From the Figure 7, it shows the accuracy of network training is 99.23%. The accuracy differs with the network design and architecture.

Utilization Estimates

Summary

Name	BRAM_18K	DSP48E	FF	LUT	URAM
DSP	-	-	-	-	-
Expression	-	-	0	12	-
FIFO	0	-	10	88	-
Instance	47	115	10639	16982	0
Memory	20	-	128	2	0
Multiplexer	-	-	-	18	-
Register	-	-	2	-	-
Total	67	115	10779	17102	0
Available	280	220	106400	53200	0
Utilization (%)	23	52	10	32	0

Table 6 : Resource Usage of CNN IP Core

Table 6 shows that 67 BRAM (23%), 115 DSP slices (52%), 10779 FF (10%) and 17102 LUT (32%) are used to generate the CNN IP core. They are not exceed the available FPGA resource requirement and free to use in the hardware system.

Figure 8 : Architecture of CNN IP Core

Figure 8 shows the structure of CNN IP core generated includes 7 AXI4 stream signals which are TDATA, TKEEP, TSTRB, TUSER, TLAST, TID and TDEST. This IP core allows dataflow of 32 bit.

Figure 9 : FPGA Block Diagram

Figure 9 shows the FPGA block diagram with CNN IP core, processor ARM and AXI DMA. The hardware design includes the Zynq7 Processing System, AXI DMA, 2 AXI Interconnect, Processor System Reset and CNN IP

Core. Zynq PS transfers the data to AXI DMA via AXI Interconnect. CNN IP Core receives the bitstream from DMA and then DMA sends it back to the processor ARM.

Figure 10 : Power Report

Figure 11 : Timing Report

Figure 10 shows the total power usage on chip is 1.879 W where 92% (1.733 W) is used for dynamic power while 8% (0.146 W) for static power. From Figure 11, it shows the timing is fulfilled with 0 failing endpoints and 0 negative slacks for setup, hold and pulse width.

Figure 12 : Face Recognition Result

From Figure 12, it shows that the system is successfully classify and predict the class of 5 input test images one by one. Class 1 means detection of Individual 1 and Class 2 means detection of Individual 2.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study proves that the designed embedded face recognition software is suitable and successful for FPGA SoC implementation with the RCNN module by using Vivado. This system achieves the FPGA resource requirement of 67 18K BRAM, 115 DSP48E, 10779 FF and 17102 LUT with power-on-chip of 1.879 Watts. Finally, 5 input images are all tested, classified and predicted correctly.

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REFERENCES

- Smriti Tikoo, Nitin Malik. 2016. Detection of Face using Viola Jones and Recognition Using Back Propagation Neural Network.
- Yashwanth M. 2019. Face-Recognition-by-CNN.
- Pranav KB, Manikandan J. 2020. Design and Evaluation of a Real-Time Face Recognition System using Convolutional Neural Networks.
- J. Zou, R. Song. 2018. Microarray camera image segmentation with Faster-RCNN.

- J. Teich. 2012. Hardware/Software Codesign: “The past, the present, and predicting the future, Proceedings”.
- L. Shang, R. Dick, N. K Jha. 2007. “SLOPES: Hardware-software cosynthesis of low-power real-time distributed embedded systems with dynamically reconfigurable FPGAs”.
- Md Mahmudul Islam. 2019. Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network and Implementation of the Neural through Zedboard Zynq.
- Tilottoma Barua. 2020. Data Transfer Performance Analysis From Programmable Logic To Processing System of Zynq 7000.
- Irene De Rose, Matteo De Silvestri, Andea Solazzo. 2016. CNN2ECST Xilinx Open Hardware Contest 2016 Report.
- Hannes Kinks. 2016. Implementating Neural Networks on Field Programmable Gate Array.
- Xiaoguang Li. 2004. A Hardware/Software Co-Design Approach For Face Recognition by Artificial Neural Networks.
- Narayan T. Deshpande, Ravishankar. 2017. Face Detection and Recognition using Viola-Jones algorithm and Fusion of PCA and ANN.
- Human Samii Moghadam. 2018. Design Exploration of an FPGA Based Face Detection Processing Core Utilizing High Level Synthesis.
- Hanh Phan-Xuan, Thuong Le-Tien, Sy Nguyen-Tan. 2019. FPGA Platform applied for Facial Expression Recognition System using Convolutional Neural Networks.
- Changpei Qiu, Xinan Wang, Tianxia Zhao, Qiuping Li, Bo Wang, Hu Wang. 2021. An FPGA-Based Convolutional Neural Network Coprocessor.
- Bing Liu, Danyin Zou, Lei Feng, hou Feng, Fing Fu, Junbao Li. 2019. An FPGA-Based CNN Accelerator Integrating Depthwise Separable Convolution.
- Smrity Bhattarai. 2017. Digital Architecture For Real-Time Face Detection For Deep Video Packet Inspection Systems.
- Li Luo, Yakun Wu, Fei Qiao, Yi Yang, Qi Wei, Xiaobo Zhou, Yongkai Fan, Shuzheng Xu, Xinjun Liu, Huazhong Yang. 2018. Design of FPGA-Based Accelerator for Convolutional Neural Network under Heterogeneous Computing Framework with OpenCL.
- Tomyslav Sledevic, Arturas Serackis. 2020. mNet2FPGA: A Design Flow for Mapping a Fixed-Point CNN to Zynq SoC FPGA.
- Linus Pettersson. 2020. Convolutional Neural Networks on FPGA and GPU on the Edge: A Comparison.
- Sheiping Zhai, Cheng Qiu, Yuanyuan Yang, Jing Li, Yiming Qiu. 2019. Design of Convolutional Neural Network Based on FPGA.
- Lester Kalms, Pedram Amini Rad, muhammad Ali, Arsany Iskander & Diana Gohringer. 2021. A Parametrizable High-Level Synthesis Library for Accelerating Neural Networks on FPGAs.
- Antonios Georgios Pistis. 2018. Design and Implementation of an FPGA-Based Convolutional Neural Network Accelerator.
- Su Yi, Hu Xiao, Sun Yongjie. 2018. FPGA Accelerating Core Design Based on XNOR Neural Network Algorithm.
- Alireza Ghaffari, Yvon Savaria. 2020. CNN2Gate: An Implementation of Convolutional Neural Networks Inference on FPGAs with Automated Design Space Exploration.
- Gianmarco Dinelli, Gabriele Meoni, Emilio Rapuano, Gionata Benelli, Luca Fanucci. 2019. An FPGA-Based Hardware Accelerator for CNNs Using On-Chip Memories Only: Design and Benchmarking with Intel Movidius Neural Compute Stick.
- P Muthu Krishnammal, T V Padmavathy, M Shakunthala, M N Vimal Kumar. 2021. Convolutional Neural Network Architecture Based on FPGA with Reduced Requirements for Parameters.
- Kamel Abdelouahab, Maxime Pelcat, Francois Berry, Jocelyn Serot. 2018. Accelerating CNN inference on FPGAs: A Survey.
- Kiruki Cosmas, Asami kenichi. 2020. Utilization of FPGA for Onboard Inference of Landmark Localization in CNN-Based Spacecraft Pose Estimation.
- Stylianios I. Venieris, Alexandros Kouris, Christos-Savvas Bouganis. 2018. Toolflows for Mapping Convolutional Neural Networks on FPGAs: A Survey and Future Directions.
- Farhad Fallah. 2019. How to Develop High-Performance Deep Neural Network Object Detection/Recognition Applications for FPGA-based Edge Devices.